

DEVELOPMENT OF A MULTIMEDIA E-LEARNING RESOURCE FOR LEARNING ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

In this period of educational technology, the English language is more popular than other world languages. In the twenty first century, teachers are essential to have a digital knowledge skill. They must be able to integrate technology in learning development. However, to obtain this skill is not easy, and may current difficulties, especially for students of English as a second language. Teaching this skill plays then a critical role, and modern techniques and methods are succeeded. The use of technology and multimedia resources come to change traditional methods to take students' attention, increase their motivation in the classroom and to succeed in classroom goals. The e-learning also used Adobe Flash and Adobe Illustrator to make some animated videos. It involved in listening, reading, and grammar which the topic focused on descriptive. The development of e-learning earned to be realized after it was authenticated by the expert, evaluated by the teacher and experienced to the

students. The explanation of a multimedia resources guide is proposed to support teachers and help students improve their speaking skill.

Keywords: *Multimedia, e-learning, Skill, Resource, Development.*

INTRODUCTION

Learning a language is a significant factor of world locations, news, scientific achievements, in short, awareness of new world movements, development of worldview. Today, almost every young person who wants to become an expert in their field is interested in learning a language. As science grows, the tendency of students, researchers and amateurs to follow this progress is also growing. Knowing the key to progress and creation of new discoveries requires learning a language these days. The more correctly the language is mastered, the more productive the result. Consequently, the issue of increasing efficiency in the language is being discussed by language researchers.

The technological revolution has reformed the world and education, and makes easier to teach and learn any foreign language. Traditional classes can be improved with the application of multimedia-based programs that turned a classroom-based session into a face to face online session. It is possible to believe then that the use of multimedia-based programs in traditional ESL and EFL classes is a successful technological average to increase students' motivation to learn.

EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY

Technology is measured a powerful tool that can change teaching and learning. It is a useful tool to strength contacts between teachers and students; it can promote new approaches for collaboration, and give teachers the chance to adopt and adapt learning experiences to satisfy students' needs. According to my explanations in one of the university classes, freedom of communication is the most important tool. This means that when the student communicates without fear of making mistakes in speech, he feels free and develops fluency, continuity and boldness. Able to demonstrate intelligible speech, although not completely correct. The lesson was conducted by an

English teacher of English nationality. The atmosphere created by the teacher in the classroom is friendly and based on independent feedback. There are no rules that students must strictly follow. Deficiencies in their language skills were addressed gently and through appropriate tools and techniques. An opportunity was given to exchange ideas in pairs on each introduced topic. A language atmosphere has been created for them to communicate easily in the language they are learning. What is important is that students establish fluency without any hesitation or anxiety.

CONCLUSIONS

The use of multimedia resources in English language teaching is an important method in education because of the opportunities to accomplish class objectives. Today, it is common to see that educators take hand of numerous technological devices in the process of language teaching and learning, because such resources make language learning more productive, effective, and communicative. Speech requires precision in some aspects and fluency in others. Neglecting fluency in pursuit of the goal of communicating in the right way in every way will definitely reduce productivity. The main thing is to be able to use each tool in its place.

REFERENCES

1. Qodirov, F. E., D. A. Akbarova, and S. H. Shokirov. "SOFTWARE FOR WORKING WITH COMPUTER GRAPHICS AND THEIR TASKS. APPLICATION OF DIGITAL IMAGE PROCESSING FIELDS." *Инновации в технологиях и образовании: сб. ст. участников XIV Меж (2021): 57.*
2. Zaripova Z. O., Akbarova D. A., Shokirov S. H. "INNOVATIONS IN ENGLISH TEACHING AT SCHOOL. USE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH" *Инновации в технологиях и образовании: сб. ст. участников XIV Меж (2021): 44.*
3. Noni Agustina, and Nugroho Budhisantosa. "Development of e-learning for English class" *SHS Web of Conferences 42, 00077 (2018), GC-TALE 2017.*